

WHAT ARE YOU GOING TO DO WITH **THAT?**

An English Student's Guide to Life after School

We all know the stereotypes...

The useless degree. Fun but impractical. O.K. as long as you want to be a barista.

Sometimes it can seem like the hardest part of an English degree is convincing your family that you're not going to be a burden on them for the rest of your life.

English grad at work?

But what if the stereotypes are wrong?

The idea that a degree in English is impractical or sets majors up for underemployment **is not true**.

In fact, **Humanities majors are less likely than others to be under-employed** (i.e. in a job that doesn't use their skills) after graduation (Hanlon et al 2024).

Over the last decade, about **95% of English grads at the U of L have said that the skills they acquired during their program were related to their current occupation**. And just over 80% said the same about the content. This is better than for many other majors.

Recent English grads on job-value of their degree

If you want to make money quick... become a **Pharmacist or Engineer**

Of course, if what you really want is to earn top-dollar right away, then English might not be for you: Pharmacists, Engineers, Nurses, and some majors in Science, Technology, and Math (STEM) have higher first-job salaries on average — though the difference is not always as much as we think (Statistics Canada 2020).

In the long haul, English majors can do as well or better than STEM

Humanists, however, tend to catch up and even exceed those gains over time. A recent study showed that graduates in applied STEM begin their careers with salaries about 50% higher than those in Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). But by age forty SSH grads were earning, on average, the same or better (Deming 2019).

There seem to be two main reasons for this:

- The **best paying mid-career jobs are in management and fields that require strong communication and critical thinking skills** (Deming 2019);
- The **best paying early-career jobs are in fields that require constant upgrading** (Deming and Noray 2018).

This means that English majors — who learn to communicate and think critically during their degrees and build on that experience through their early jobs and professional programs — can find themselves well positioned for mid-career positions just as their more technologically-focussed friends find the relevance of their technical skills begin to fade (Deming and Noray 2018).

Adult Workers' Use of English-Related Skills on the Job (adapted from AAAS 2021, figure 15).

And who says there's anything wrong with being a barista, anyway?

In the end, the most important thing for many people is satisfaction: are you studying things you are interested in and can help you grow as a person? Are you working in a field that allows you to use your talents and keep a roof over your head? Perhaps it sometimes takes English majors a little longer to get started — through early jobs that provide more experience than money, or additional professional and graduate study. But like many Humanities grads they do well where it counts: happy with their life choices and doing what they enjoy (Robson et al. 2023).

Read more

- American Academy of Arts and Sciences. 2021. "State of the Humanities 2021: Workforce & Beyond." November 7, 2021.
- Deming, David J. 2019. "In the Salary Race, Engineers Sprint but English Majors Endure." *The New York Times*, September 20, 2019.
- Deming, David J., and Kadeem L. Noray. 2018. "STEM Careers and the Changing Skill Requirements of Work." National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Hanlon, Aaron, Eric Hayot, and Anna Kornbluh. 2024. "Underemployment." Humanities Works. 2024.
- Statistics Canada. 2020. "Which Bachelor's Degree Programs Were Associated with the Highest Pay Prior to the COVID-19 Pandemic? A Focus on Very Detailed Fields of Study." August 24.
- Robson, James, Emily Murphy, Nuzha Nuseibeh, Alice Tawell, and Ben Hart, 2023. *The Value of the Humanities: Understanding the Career Destinations of Oxford Humanities Graduates*